

Standard E. M. F. of the Cell, $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \right| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \left| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \right| \text{Q.H.} \left| \text{Pt} \right.$
Pt and Standard Electrode Potential of the $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \text{Br}^- \right.$
Electrode at 5°, 15°, 25°, and 35°.

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The standard e.m.f. of the cell, $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \right| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \left| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr.Q.H.}} \right| \text{Pt}$, where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone, has been determined at 5°, 15°, 25°, and 35°, and has been found to be 0.6349, 0.6315, 0.6283 and 0.6263 volt respectively. The calculated standard electrode potential of $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \text{Br}^- \right.$ from the known electrode potential of quinhydrone comes out to be 0.0795, 0.0756, 0.0714 and 0.0661 volt at 5°, 15°, 25°, and 35° respectively. The activity coefficients of hydrobromic acid (0.005–0.100) has been calculated, and is in agreement with earlier results.

It is proposed to determine the dissociation constant of some bromides of bivalent metals. These determinations will require a knowledge of the standard e.m.f. of the cell, $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \right| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr}} \left| \underset{(c)}{\text{HBr.Q.H.}} \right| \text{Pt}$. This forms the basis of the paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Constant boiling acid prepared from G.R. quality hydrobromic acid and double distilled water were used in preparing the stock solution. The concentration of the stock solution determined volumetrically with borax and gravimetrically as silver bromide agreed with one another. Measurements were made in air thermostats whose temperature was constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

The $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \text{Br}^- \right.$ electrodes were prepared by the thermal method recommended by Hetzer, Robinson and Bates¹. On inter comparison in 0.05 M KBr and 0.05 M HBr, the e.m.f. developed did not exceed 0.05 mv. The quinhydrone half cell was prepared as described earlier². The measuring flasks containing the experimental solutions were placed in a vessel which was connected to a vacuum pump. As soon as the solution started boiling the pumping was stopped and the solutions were allowed to remain in this condition for about 2 hrs. The loss in volume caused due to evaporation was made up at the experimental temperature at which the volume of the solution was made up to 500 ml. Final traces of oxygen were removed by bubbling nitrogen and measurements were made as in an earlier paper². Duplicates agreed amongst themselves within 0.1 mv. In a few cases, the differences went up to 0.16 mv. []_T denotes stoichiometric concentration, in gms. mol/litre. The e.m.f. values given in Table I are the mean of the duplicates.

1. H. B. Hetzer, R. A. Robinson and R. G. Bates, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1423.
2. L. Sharma, G. Sahu and B. Prasad, *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 580.

TABLE I

[HBr] _r	Observed e.m.f. in volt			
	5°	15°	25°	35°
0.005	0.37737	0.36470	0.35236	0.34104
0.010	0.40946	0.39800	0.38660	0.37640
0.020	0.44131	0.43085	0.42059	0.41162
0.035	0.46683	0.45713	0.44788	0.43970
0.050	0.48287	0.47382	0.46509	0.45766
0.075	0.50145	0.49294	0.48476	0.47777
0.100	0.51448	0.50652	0.49881	0.49195

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell Ag | AgBr.HBr | HBr | HBr Q.H. | Pt is given by the equation;

$$E - \frac{RT}{F} \log_e [H^+] \times [Br^-] + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = E^\circ + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} B\mu \quad (1)$$

The values of A (Debye-Hückel constant) taken are the same as in an earlier paper². By the method described by Prasad and coworkers² E° was found to be +0.6349, +0.6315, +0.6285 and +0.6266 volt at 5°, 15°, 25°, and 35° respectively. These values of E° are on the molarity scale. The conversion of E° to $E^\circ(m)$ on the molarity scale in these cells will be governed by the equation, $E^\circ(m) = E^\circ + \frac{2 \times 2.3026 RT}{F} \log \rho$ where ρ is the density of water. The values of $E^\circ(m)$ for this cell come out to be 0.6349, 0.6315, 0.6283 and 0.6263 at 5°, 15°, 25°, and 35° after necessary conversion. Our values of $E^\circ(m)$ for Ag | AgBr Br⁻ calculated from the accepted values of $E^\circ(m)$ of the quinhydrone electrode³ are given in Table II along with the values of other standard authors. Fifth place has been omitted from all values.

TABLE II

Standard Electrode Potential of Ag/AgBr Br⁻
in volt (Molality scale)

	5°	15°	25°	35°
Present work	0.0795	0.0756	0.0714	0.0661
H., R., and B ¹	0.0796	0.0757	0.0711	0.0659
H., K., and D ⁴	0.0796	0.0756	0.0710	0.0658
O., and F. ⁵	0.0799	0.0760	0.0713	0.0660
H. and D. ⁶	—	—	0.0713	—
T., G. and L. ⁷	—	—	0.0716	—

3. R. G. Bates, "Electrometric pH Determinations", p. 175, Wiley, New York 1954.
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5. B. B. Owen and L. Foering, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1575.
6. H. S. Harned and John G. Donelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1280.
7. M. B. Towns, R. S. Greeley and M. H. Lietzke, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1861.

TABLE III

Activity coefficient of hydrobromic acid.

[HBr] _T	5°	15°	25°	35°
0.005	0.931	0.930	0.928	0.927
0.010	0.908	0.906	0.904	0.902
0.020	0.880	0.878	0.875	0.873
0.035	0.856	0.853	0.849	0.846
0.050	0.834	0.836	0.832	0.828
0.075	0.823	0.818	0.813	0.809
0.100	0.813	0.808	0.802	0.796

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